

Effect of solvents on the electrochemical behaviour of copper(II,III) complexes with morpholinedithiocarbamate ligand

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Abstract : The electrochemical behaviour of square planar $[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ (green), **1** and $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]$ (brown), **2** (morph-dtc⁻ = morpholinedithiocarbamate anion) has been studied in dichloromethane (DCM), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethylformamide (DMF) and acetone containing 0.1 M TBAP as supporting electrolyte at a platinum disc working electrode using cyclic voltammetry. Two one-electron redox couples ($\text{Cu}^{3+/2+}$) and ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) corresponding to $[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]^+ + e^- \rightarrow [\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]$ in the positive potential region and $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2] + e^- \rightarrow [\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]^-$ in the negative potential region have been observed in DCM and DMSO media. In DMF and acetone, however, only a single quasireversible couple followed by an intense irreversible anodic peak, have been observed in the positive potential region. The present electrochemical studies reveal that the redox properties of complex **1** differ significantly in these solvents. It is observed that the ease of reduction ($\text{Cu}^{3+/2+}$) of this complex decreases in the order : acetone (E^{0} = 625 mV) \rightarrow DCM (E^{0} = 605 mV) \rightarrow DMSO (E^{0} = 500 mV) \rightarrow DMF (E^{0} = 380 mV).

Keywords : Electrochemistry, copper(II,III) complexes, dithiocarbamates, cyclic voltammetry.

The coordination chemistry of high-oxidation state transition metal complexes is an area of considerable importance, because of their biological significance as models of redox enzymes and their potentially useful properties as catalytic oxidants¹. One important feature of dithiocarbamate ligands is their ability to stabilize both high and low formal oxidation states (e.g. copper(III), nickel(IV) and iron(IV))². This is as a result of the delocalization that the ligand provides (Fig. 1) and the consequential high electron density the sulfur donors present³. Dithiocarbamates, their metal complexes and their oxidation products, thiouramdisulfides have had numerous industrial uses; for example, they have acted as lubricants, antioxidants, fungicides and accelerators for rubber vulcanization and as drugs in medicine⁴.

The dithiocarbamate (dtc) ligand has proved to be an extremely versatile and robust motif for metal-directed self-assembly. Its ease of formation and wide ranging coordination chemistry has led to the formation of an array of novel and complex supramolecular architectures. The use of the dithiocarbamate ligand has recently expanded to stabilizing gold nanoparticles and preparing multimetallic wires and arrays⁵.

In our earlier paper we reported the cyclic voltammetric studies of some copper(II,III)-dithiocarbamates⁶. Here we report the electrochemical behaviour of copper(II) and copper(III) complexes with morpholinedithiocarbamate bidentate monoanionic ligand (morph-dtc⁻), viz. $[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ (green), **1** and $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]$ (brown), **2**. Both these complexes have square planar structures in which Cu^{II} and Cu^{III} are coordinated to four sulphur donor atoms⁷.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical studies of $[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$, **1** were carried out in dichloromethane (DCM), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethylformamide (DMF) and acetone containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as a supporting electrolyte at a platinum disc working electrode using cyclic voltammetry (CV) technique. The CV experiments were also performed for $[\text{Cu}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]$, **2** in DCM/0.1 M TBAP medium for the sake of comparison. Typical cyclic voltammograms of **1** in DCM, DMSO and DMF are shown in Figs. 2(a,b,c) at a scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹ and CV data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Resonance structures of the morph-dtc⁻ ligand.

Table 1. CV data for [Cu(morph-dtc)₂]ClO₄ in DCM and DMSO/0.1 M TBAP

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	First couple (Cu ^{3+/2+})					Second couple (Cu ^{2+/+})					<i>E</i> _{pc1} /mV
	<i>E</i> _{pc1} (mV)	<i>E</i> _{pa1} (mV)	<i>E</i> ^{0'} (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	<i>I</i> _{pa1} / <i>I</i> _{pc1}	<i>E</i> _{pc2} (mV)	<i>E</i> _{pa2} (mV)	<i>E</i> ^{0'} (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	<i>I</i> _{pa2} / <i>I</i> _{pc2}	
In DCM :											
25	580	630	605	50	1.8	-480	-410	-445	70	0.5	
100	580	630	605	50	1.9	-510	-380	-445	130	0.5	
200	580	630	605	50	1.9	-530	-360	-445	170	0.5	
300	580	630	605	50	1.9	-550	-340	-445	210	0.5	
400	570	630	600	60	2.0	-560	-330	-445	230	0.5	
500	560	640	600	80	2.0	-580	-320	-450	260	0.5	
600	560	640	600	80	2.0	-590	-310	-450	280	0.5	
In DMSO :											
25	470	530	500	60	2.7	-390	-300	-345	90	0.8	-50
50	470	530	500	60	2.8	-390	-300	-345	90	0.7	-50
100	470	530	500	60	3.0	-400	-290	-345	110	0.7	-60
200	470	530	500	60	3.0	-430	-290	-360	140	0.7	-90
300	470	530	500	60	3.2	-450	-280	-365	170	0.6	-100
400	470	530	500	60	3.0	-460	-270	-365	190	0.6	-100
500	470	530	500	60	2.6	-460	-270	-365	190	0.5	-110

$E^{0'} = 1/2 (E_{pc} + E_{pa})$.

Table 2. CV data for [Cu(morph-dtc)₂]ClO₄ in DMF and acetone/0.1 M TBAP

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	<i>E</i> _{pc1} (mV)	<i>E</i> _{pa1} (mV)	<i>E</i> ^{0'} (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	<i>I</i> _{pa1} / <i>I</i> _{pc1}	<i>E</i> _{pa2'} (mV)
In DMF :						
50	300	470	385	170	1.2	700
100	270	490	380	220	1.4	700
200	230	500	365	270	1.5	700
300	230	500	365	270	1.4	700
400	230	510	370	280	1.4	720
500	230	520	375	280	2.0	720
600	220	530	375	310	2.7	720
In acetone :						
25	600	650	625	50	1.5	850
50	600	650	625	50	1.6	850
100	600	650	625	50	1.7	850
200	600	650	625	50	1.8	850
300	600	650	625	50	2.0	875
400	600	650	625	50	2.1	900
500	600	670	635	70	2.2	900
600	600	670	635	70	2.4	925

In DCM, a negative scan started from +0.75 V in the potential range 1.0 to -0.80 V vs SCE displayed two one-electron redox couples : the first couple in the positive potential region has formal potential, *E*^{0'} = 605 mV vs SCE (*E*_{pc1} = 580 mV, *E*_{pa1} = 630 mV, ΔE_p = 50 mV) and is assigned to a well-defined electrochemically reversible one-electron transfer Cu^{III} → Cu^{II}, while the second couple

in the negative potential region with *E*^{0'} = -445 mV vs SCE (*E*_{pc2} = -510 mV, *E*_{pa2} = -380 mV, ΔE_p = 130 mV) is assigned to a quasi-reversible one-electron transfer Cu^{II} → Cu^I (Table 1 and Fig. 2(a))^{6,8-10}. It is interesting to note that the anodic to cathodic current ratio, *I*_{pa1}/*I*_{pc1} is greater than 1.0 for the first couple (Cu^{3+/2+}), indicating weak adsorption^{8,10} of the electro-generated Cu^{II}-dtc complex species on the surface of the platinum electrode, while the current ratio (*I*_{pa2}/*I*_{pc2}) for the second couple (Cu^{2+/+}) is less than unity, indicating that the electron transfer is followed by a chemical reaction (EC mechanism)^{9,10}. The plots of *I*_{pc1} or *I*_{pc2} vs square root of the scan rate (*v*^{1/2}) gives a straight line passing through origin, showing that both these reduction processes are diffusion-controlled. Similarly, a positive scan initiated from +150 mV vs SCE in the potential range 1.0 to -0.80 V for complex 2 resulted almost a similar cyclic voltammogram with similar values of different CV parameters as observed for complex 1.

The cyclic voltammogram of 1 in DMSO also shows (Fig. 2b) two one-electron redox couples with *E*_{pc1} = 470 mV, *E*_{pa1} = 530 mV, *E*^{0'} = 500 mV, ΔE_p = 60 mV for Cu^{3+/2+} reversible couple and *E*_{pc2} = -400 mV, *E*_{pa2} = -290 mV, *E*^{0'} = -345 mV, ΔE_p = 110 mV for Cu^{2+/+} quasi-reversible couple. In addition to this, a third irreversible intense reduction peak *c*₁' also appeared at *E*_{pc1'} = -60 mV (Table 1 and Fig. 2(b)).

The cyclic voltammograms for 1 in DMF and acetone are similar but the values of peak potentials differ markedly

Fig 2. Cyclic voltammograms of $[Cu^{III}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]ClO_4$ in DCM (a), DMSO (b) and DMF (c), containing 0.1 M TBAP at $v = 100 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$.

in these two solvents. A negative scan from +520 mV (potential range +0.95 to -0.35 V) shows one quasi-reversible couple with $E_{pc1} = 270 \text{ mV}$, $E_{pa1} = 490 \text{ mV}$, $\Delta E_p = 220 \text{ mV}$ and $E_{pa2} = 700 \text{ mV}$ vs SCE in DMF medium, while in acetone the values of E_{pc1} , E_{pa1} , ΔE_p and E_{pa2} are 600, 650, 50 and 850 mV, respectively (Table 2 and Fig. 2(c)).

It is worth mentioning that complex $[Cu^{III}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]ClO_4$ (green) is soluble in water, the aqueous solution, on keeping for some time, deposits a brown precipitate, which was identified as $[Cu^{II}(\text{morph-dtc})_2]^7$. We found that complex 1 is partly soluble in the solvents selected in the present study and on keeping the solutions for few hours, a brown precipitate appeared in all solvents except in dichloromethane. All the solutions of these complexes were

therefore, filtered through gravimetric filter paper before purging N₂ gas.

Electrochemical studies reported here reveal that the redox properties of [Cu(morph-dtc)₂]ClO₄ differ significantly in DCM, DMSO, DMF and acetone. A perusal of Tables 1 and 2 and Figs. 2(a,b,c) clearly shows that the ease of reduction of complex 1 decreases in the order : acetone ($E^{\circ} = 625$ mV) → DCM ($E^{\circ} = 605$ mV) → DMSO ($E^{\circ} = 500$ mV) → DMF ($E^{\circ} = 380$ mV).

Experimental

Spectroscopic/or AnalaR grade solvents were procured from different commercial sources and used as such. TBAP was obtained from Fluka Chemika, Switzerland and was used as the supporting electrolyte in the present electrochemical studies. Morph-dtc Na₂H₂O and Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. and used as such.

The complexes [Cu^{II}(morph-dtc)₂] (brown) and [Cu^{III}(morph-dtc)₂]ClO₄ (green) were prepared according to literature procedures^{7,11}. All the experimental details have already been described in our previous papers⁹. Platinum disc electrode was used as working electrode, saturated calomel electrode as reference and platinum wire was used as auxiliary electrode. All the experiments were performed at 20 ± 0.5 °C.

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